

On the Complexity of inverting Shortest-Path Routing with Connected Waypoint Constraints

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Abstract—We prove that finding link weights for Shortest Path Routing (SPR) that satisfy a set of connected waypoint constraints is NP-complete.

I. INVERTING SPR UNDER CONNECTED WAYPOINTS

Theorem 1.1: Deciding whether there exists a set of link weights for SPR such that a set of *connected* waypoint properties are satisfied is NP-complete.

Call et al. has shown a construction from One-In-Three 3SAT (X3SAT) to a similar problem as Theorem 1.1, where we require certain edges $E_v^+ \subset E$ to be on the shortest-path tree towards node v , and other edges $E_v^- \subset E$ not to be on the shortest-path tree towards v [1]. In the following, we use a very similar construction to prove Theorem 1.1. First, we show two components used in the construction in Lemma 1.1 and Lemma 1.2. Then, we present a transformation from X3SAT to Inverse Shortest Path Routing (ISPR) with connected waypoint properties and show that the transformed problem has a solution if and only if the original problem is solvable. However, we can transform any problem instance with edge waypoints into one with node waypoints by replacing each edge with a node with two edges connected to it.

Lemma 1.1: Let $G = (V, E)$ be a directed graph where $s_1, s_2, t_1, t_2, v_1, v_2 \in V$, and $(s_1, v_1), (s_2, v_1), (s_1, v_2), (s_2, v_2) \in E$. There cannot exist any set of link weights w , such that the following waypoints are satisfied: $wp(s_1, t_1) = (s_1, v_1)$, $wp(s_1, t_2) = (s_1, v_2)$, $wp(s_2, t_1) = (s_2, v_2)$, and $wp(s_2, t_2) = (s_2, v_1)$ (as drawn in Fig. 1).

Proof of Lemma 1.1: We prove Lemma 3 by contradiction. Assume there exists a set of link weights w that satisfy the waypoints (cf. Fig. 1). Thus, the following inequalities must hold:

$$\begin{aligned} w(s_1, v_1) + x_{v_1, t_1} &< w(s_1, v_2) + x_{v_2, t_1} \\ w(s_2, v_2) + x_{v_2, t_1} &< w(s_2, v_1) + x_{v_1, t_1} \\ w(s_1, v_2) + x_{v_2, t_2} &< w(s_1, v_1) + x_{v_1, t_2} \\ w(s_2, v_1) + x_{v_1, t_2} &< w(s_2, v_2) + x_{v_2, t_2} \end{aligned}$$

The second and third inequalities can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned} w(s_2, v_2) + x_{v_2, t_1} - w(s_2, v_1) &< x_{v_1, t_1} \\ w(s_1, v_2) + x_{v_2, t_2} - w(s_1, v_1) &< x_{v_1, t_2} \end{aligned}$$

By substituting the second and the third equation into the first and the fourth, and subtracting x_{v_2, t_1} , and x_{v_2, t_2} , respectively, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} w(s_1, v_1) + w(s_2, v_2) - w(s_2, v_1) &< w(s_1, v_2) \\ w(s_2, v_1) + w(s_1, v_2) - w(s_1, v_1) &< w(s_2, v_2) \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 1. Illustration of graph G for Lemma 1.1 with all waypoints. Red arrows show waypoints towards t_1 , while blue arrows show waypoints towards t_2 .

Fig. 2. Illustration of graph G for Lemma 1.2 with all waypoints. Red arrows show waypoints towards t_1 , blue arrows show waypoints towards t_2 , and green arrows represent waypoints towards t_3 .

We then rearrange terms in both equations to get:

$$\begin{aligned} w(s_1, v_1) - w(s_1, v_2) &< w(s_2, v_1) - w(s_2, v_2) \\ w(s_1, v_1) - w(s_1, v_2) &> w(s_2, v_1) - w(s_2, v_2) \end{aligned}$$

These two equations are equivalent to saying $a < b \wedge a > b$, yielding the contradiction. ■

Lemma 1.2: Let $G = (V, E)$ be a directed graph, where $t_1, t_2, t_3, s_1, s_2, v_1, v_2, v_3 \in V$, and $(s_1, v_1), (s_2, v_1), (s_1, v_2), (s_2, v_2), (s_1, v_3), (s_2, v_3) \in E$. There cannot exist a set of link weights w such that the following waypoints are satisfied: $wp(s_1, t_1) = (s_1, v_1)$, $wp(s_1, t_2) = (s_1, v_2)$, $wp(s_1, t_3) = (s_1, v_3)$, $wp(s_2, t_1) = (s_2, v_2)$, $wp(s_2, t_2) = (s_2, v_3)$, and $wp(s_2, t_3) = (s_2, v_1)$ (as drawn in Fig. 2).

Proof of Lemma 1.2: The proof is very similar to Lemma 1.2. Assume, for the sake of contradiction, that there exists a set of link weights w where all waypoint constraints are satisfied. This yields the following inequalities:

$$\begin{aligned} w(s_1, v_1) + x_{v_1, t_1} &< w(s_1, v_2) + x_{v_2, t_1} \\ w(s_1, v_2) + x_{v_2, t_2} &< w(s_1, v_3) + x_{v_3, t_2} \\ w(s_1, v_3) + x_{v_3, t_3} &< w(s_1, v_1) + x_{v_1, t_3} \\ w(s_2, v_2) + x_{v_2, t_1} &< w(s_2, v_1) + x_{v_1, t_1} \\ w(s_2, v_3) + x_{v_3, t_2} &< w(s_2, v_2) + x_{v_2, t_2} \\ w(s_2, v_1) + x_{v_1, t_3} &< w(s_2, v_3) + x_{v_3, t_3} \end{aligned}$$

The third, fourth and fifth inequalities can be rewritten as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} w(s_2, v_2) + x_{v_2, t_1} - w(s_2, v_1) &< x_{v_1, t_1} \\ w(s_2, v_3) + x_{v_3, t_2} - w(s_2, v_2) &< x_{v_2, t_2} \\ w(s_2, v_1) + x_{v_1, t_3} - w(s_2, v_3) &< x_{v_3, t_3} \end{aligned}$$

We then substitute the 4th, 5th, and 6th inequality into the first, second, and third. In addition, in each inequality, we subtract the common term x_{v_2, t_1} , x_{v_3, t_2} , and x_{v_1, t_3} , respectively. Finally, we rearrange some terms to get:

$$\begin{aligned} w(s_1, v_1) - w(s_2, v_1) &< w(s_1, v_2) - w(s_2, v_2) \\ w(s_1, v_2) - w(s_2, v_2) &< w(s_1, v_3) - w(s_2, v_3) \\ w(s_1, v_3) - w(s_2, v_3) &< w(s_1, v_1) - w(s_2, v_1) \end{aligned}$$

Now, we introduce the substitution $y_i = w(s_1, v_i) - w(s_2, v_i)$ for all $i \in 1, 2, 3$. It follows that $y_1 < y_2 < y_3 < y_1$, yielding the contradiction. ■

Definition 1.1 (ISPR): An instance of the ISPR problem is defined as $I_{ISPR} = (G, wp)$, where $G = (V, E)$ is a directed graph with vertices V and edges E , and $wp : (V \times V) \mapsto E$ is a set of waypoints that is *connected*. A solution to I_{ISPR} is a set of edge weights $w : E \mapsto \mathbb{R}^+$, such that every waypoint property is satisfied, i.e., for each $(s, t, \omega) \in wp$, the shortest s - t -path contains the waypoint $\omega \in p_{s,t}$.

Definition 1.2 (X3SAT): An instance of the X3SAT problem is a tuple $I_{X3SAT} = (U, C)$, where U is a set of variables, and C is a set of clauses. Each clause $C_i = (u_a, u_b, u_c) \in C$ is a set of three (non-identical) variables from U . The problem instance I_{X3SAT} is in normal form if the clauses are ordered alphabetically, and no two clauses contain the same two variables¹. A solution to I_{X3SAT} is an assignment of boolean values to each variable $u_i \in U$, such that, for any clause $C' = (u_a, u_b, u_c) \in C$, exactly one of the three variables u_a , u_b and u_c are set to *true*. X3SAT is NP-Complete [2].

Proof of Theorem 1.1: ISPR is in NP because a non-deterministic algorithm can simply guess a set of link weights w . Then, it can check whether w satisfies all required waypoints wp by computing the shortest path for all pairs of nodes in the network (for which polynomial-time algorithms exist).

We now transform X3SAT to ISPR with waypoints, relying on the two components presented in Lemmas 1.1 and 1.2. We show that the constructed problem is solvable if and only if there exists a solution to the original problem.

Let $I_{X3SAT} = (U, C)$ be an instance of the X3SAT problem. We now construct $I_{ISPR} = (G, wp)$ based on I_{X3SAT} , as illustrated in Fig. 3. The basic idea is that any path from S to a variable $u \in U$ traverse either u^+ or u^- . If the path traverses u^+ , we set u to *true*, and *false* if it goes via u^- . Let V be the set of nodes constructed as follows:

- Add the start node S .
- Add, for all $u \in U$, a node u, u', u^-, u^+ .
- Add, for all $C_i = (u_a, u_b, u_c) \in C$, the nodes $C_i, C_i^{u_a}, C_i^{u_b}$ and $C_i^{u_c}$.

Then, let E be the set of edges constructed as follows (without adding any duplicate edges):

- For all $u \in U$, add the edges (u^-, u') , (u^+, u') , and (u', u) . Also, add the edges (S, u^-) , (S, u^+) from the start node.
- For all clauses $C_i = (u_a, u_b, u_c) \in C$, and for all $u \in u_a, u_b, u_c$, add edges (C_i, u^-) , $(C_i^{u_a}, u^+)$, $(C_i^{u_b}, u^+)$, and $(C_i^{u_c}, u^+)$ to the graph.
- For all $u_a, u_b \in U$ where $u_a \neq u_b$, add the edges (u_a^-, u_b) , and (u_a^+, u_b) to the graph.

Then, we add the following waypoints (as shown in Fig. 4). For each clause $C_i = (u_a, u_b, u_c) \in C$, we define the function n_i that rotates the variables in C_i , such that $n_i(u_a) = u_b$, $n_i(u_b) = u_c$, and $n_i(u_c) = u_a$.

¹Assume C contains two clauses (u_1, u_2, u_3) , and (u_1, u_2, u_4) . Then, any valid solution to I_{X3SAT} would assign the same value to u_3 and u_4 . Hence, any occurrence of u_4 could be replaced by u_3 without changing the problem.

Fig. 3. Example Network $G = (V, E)$ that corresponds to the X3SAT problem that has only a single clause: $C_1 = (a, b, c)$.

Fig. 4. Example network $G = (V, E)$ with all waypoints that correspond to the X3SAT problem that has only a single clause $C_1 = (a, b, c)$

- 1) $\forall u \in U : wp(S, u) = (u', u)$. This waypointing constraint ensures S to choose either u^- or u^+ .
- 2) $\forall u \in U : wp(u^\pm, u) = (u^\pm, u')$.
- 3) $\forall u, v \in U, u \neq v : wp(u^\pm, v) = (u^\pm, v)$.
- 4) $\forall C_i \in C, \forall u \in C_i : wp(C_i, u) = (C_i, n_i(u)^-)$.
- 5) $\forall C_i \in C, \forall u \in C_i : wp(C_i^u, u) = (C_i^u, n_i(u)^+)$. In other words, for all clauses $C_i = (u_a, u_b, u_c) \in C$, we add the following constraints:
 - $wp(C_i^a, u_a) = (C_i^a, u_b^+)$, and
 - $wp(C_i^b, u_b) = (C_i^b, u_c^+)$, and
 - $wp(C_i^c, u_c) = (C_i^c, u_a^+)$.
- 6) $\forall C_i \in C, \forall u \in C_i : wp(C_i^u, n_i(u)) = (C_i^u, u^+)$. In other words, for all clauses $C_i = (u_a, u_b, u_c) \in C$, we add the following constraints:
 - $wp(C_i^a, u_b) = (C_i^a, u_a^+)$, and
 - $wp(C_i^b, u_c) = (C_i^b, u_b^+)$, and
 - $wp(C_i^c, u_a) = (C_i^c, u_c^+)$.

Note, that all waypoints are *connected*. This construction can be done in polynomial time, as $G = (V, E)$ contains $\mathcal{O}(|U| + |C|)$ nodes, and $\mathcal{O}(|U|^2 + |C|)$ edges and waypoints.

For the remainder of this proof, given any weighted graph $G' = (V, E, w)$, we will denote, for all $u \in U$, the path $p_{S,u}$ to be one of the shortest S - u -path in G' , and $P_{S,u}$ to be the set of all shortest S - u -paths in G' . Further, we write $e \in P_{S,u}$ to indicate that edge e is contained in every path of $P_{S,u}$.

We now present five properties for any weighted graph $G' = (V, E, w)$ that satisfy all waypoint constraints wp as described in the construction above. We then prove each property individually.

- 1) $\forall u \in U, \forall p \in P_{S,u} : (S, u^-) \in p \vee (S, u^+) \in p$.
- 2) $\forall C_i = (u_a, u_b, u_c) \in C : (S, u_a^+) \in P_{S,u_a} \vee (S, u_b^+) \in P_{S,u_b} \vee (S, u_c^+) \in P_{S,u_c}$.
- 3) $\forall C_i \in C, \forall u \in C_i : \neg((S, u^+) \in P_{S,u} \wedge (S, n_i(u)^+) \in P_{S,n_i(u)})$. In other words, for all clauses $C_i = (u_a, u_b, u_c) \in C$, the following holds:
 - a) $(S, u_a^+) \in P_{S,u_a} \oplus (S, u_b^+) \in P_{S,u_b}$, and
 - b) $(S, u_b^+) \in P_{S,u_b} \oplus (S, u_c^+) \in P_{S,u_c}$, and
 - c) $(S, u_c^+) \in P_{S,u_c} \oplus (S, u_a^+) \in P_{S,u_a}$.
- 4) $\forall C_i = (u_a, u_b, u_c) \in C : 1 = ((S, u_a^+) \in P_{S,u_a}) + ((S, u_b^+) \in P_{S,u_b}) + ((S, u_c^+) \in P_{S,u_c})$. In other words, for all $C_i = (u_a, u_b, u_c) \in C$, exactly one of the sets P_{S,u_a}, P_{S,u_b} , or P_{S,u_c} contains the edge $(S, u_a^+), (S, u_b^+)$, or (S, u_c^+) , respectively.
- 5) $\forall u \in U : (S, u^+) \in P_{S,u} \iff (S, u^-) \notin P_{S,u}$.

The proof for each of these five properties follows directly from Lemmas 1.1 and 1.2:

- 1) W.o.l.g., let $u \in U$. Since $wp(S, u) - (u', u)$, Any shortest S - u -path on G' must traverse node u' . Further, since $\forall v \in U, u \neq v, wp(v^-, u) = (v^-, u)$, S cannot reach either u^+ or u^- via v^+ or v^- . Therefore, for any shortest S - u -path $p \in P_{S,u}$, either $(S, u^+) \in p$ or $(S, u^-) \in p$.
- 2) W.o.l.g., let $C_i = (u_a, u_b, u_c) \in C$. We will prove Property 2 by contradiction. Assume $(S, u_a^+) \notin P_{S,u_a} \wedge (S, u_b^+) \notin P_{S,u_b} \wedge (S, u_c^+) \notin P_{S,u_c}$. As a result, by Property 1, $(S, u_a^-) \in P_{S,u_a} \wedge (S, u_b^-) \in P_{S,u_b} \wedge (S, u_c^-) \in P_{S,u_c}$. We can now apply Lemma 1.2 to the sub-graph with $s_1 = S, s_2 = C_i, v_1 = u_a^-, v_2 = u_b^-,$ and $v_3 = u_c^-$, as wp contains $wp(C_i, u_a) = (C_i, u_b)^-, wp(C_i, u_b) = (C_i, u_c)^-,$ and $wp(C_i, u_c) = (C_i, u_a)^-$, which leads to the contradiction.
- 3) The argumentation for the three statements is identical. We will prove the first statement by contradiction. W.o.l.g., let $C_i = (u_a, u_b, u_c) \in C$. For the sake of contradiction, assume $(S, u_a^+) \in P_{S,u_a} \wedge (S, u_b^+) \in P_{S,u_b}$. We can apply Lemma 1.1 to the sub-graph with $s_1 = S, s_2 = C_i^{u_a}, v_1 = v_a^+,$ and $v_2 = v_b^+,$ as wp contains $wp(C_i^{u_a}, u_a) = (C_i^{u_a}, u_b^+),$ and $wp(C_i^{u_a}, u_b) = (C_i^{u_a}, u_a^+),$ which leads to the contradiction. We can use the same argument for the second and third statement, but with $C_i^{u_b}$, and $C_i^{u_c}$, respectively.
- 4) Property 4 directly follows from Property 2 and 3. W.o.l.g., let $C_i \in C$. Due to Property 2, for all $u \in C_i$, at least one of $(S, u^+) \in P_{S,u}$ holds. Further, because of Property 3, there cannot exist a pair $u, v \in C_i$ with $u \neq v$, for which both $(S, u^+) \in P_{S,u}$ and $(S, v^+) \in P_{S,v}$. It follows, that for exactly one variable $u \in C_i, (S, u^+) \in P_{S,u}$.

TABLE I
ASSIGNMENT OF LINK WEIGHTS

#	Iteration	Link	w	condition
1	$\forall u \in U$	(S, u^-)	10	
2		(S, u^+)	10	
3		(u^+, u')	3	if $u \in U_t$
			15	otherwise
4		(u^-, u')	3	if $u \notin U_t$
			15	otherwise
5		(u', u)	2	
6	$\forall C_i \in C, u \in C_i$	(C, u^-)	3	if $u \in U_t$
			6	if $n_i(u) \in U_t$
			9	otherwise
7		(C_u, u^+)	3	if $n_i(u) \in U_t$
			9	otherwise
8		$(C_u, n_i(u)^+)$	3	if $u \in U_t$
			9	otherwise
9	$\forall u, v \in U, u \neq v$	(v^+, u)	7	
10		(v^-, u)	7	if $\exists i : v = n_i(u)$
			15	otherwise

- 5) W.o.l.g., let $C_i = (u_a, u_b, u_c) \in C$. Further, w.o.l.g., assume that $(S, u_a^+) \in P_{S,u_a}, (S, u_b^+) \notin P_{S,u_b}$, and $(S, u_c^+) \notin P_{S,u_c}$ (by applying Property 4). By applying Property 1, we get $(S, u_b^-) \in P_{S,u_b}$ and $(S, u_c^-) \in P_{S,u_c}$. For the sake of contradiction, assume that $(S, u^-) \in P_{S,u}$. By applying Lemma 1.1 in the same way as in the proof of Property 2, we arrive at the contradiction.

We will now use those five properties to prove I_{X3SAT} has a solution if and only if I_{ISPR} is solvable in two steps. First, we show that we can construct a solution to I_{X3SAT} from a valid solution to I_{ISPR} in polynomial time. Then, we show the other direction—that we can construct a solution to I_{ISPR} from a valid solution to I_{X3SAT} in polynomial time.

Let $G' = (V, A, w)$ be a solution to I_{ISPR} . We will now show how to construct a solution to I_{X3SAT} from G' in polynomial time. For each variable $u \in U$, assign u to *true* if $(S, u^+) \in P_{S,u}$ and to *false* otherwise. By Property 4 and 5, for each clause $C_i \in C$, for exactly one variable $u \in C, (S, u^+) \in P_{S,u}$, while for all $v \in C$ where $u \neq v, (S, v^-) \in P_{S,v}$. Hence, for each clause, exactly one variable is set to *true*.

Let $U_t \subset U$ be a solution to I_{X3SAT} , where $u \in U_t$ if it is set to *true*. We will now show how to construct a solution to I_{ISPR} by generating $G' = (V, E, w)$ with a set of link weights w . Table I shows how we assign weights to each link. In the following, we will show why this set of link weights is a valid solution for I_{ISPR} , which finally concludes the proof of Theorem 1.1. We start by collecting three observations:

- 1) $\forall u \in U$, the shortest S - u^\pm -path is the path $\langle (S, u^\pm) \rangle$ as all outgoing edges of S have equal link weights.
- 2) $\forall u, v \in U$ with $u \neq v$, there are three possible paths from u^\pm to v^\pm that neither traverse u nor v . $\langle (u^\pm, S), (S, v^\pm) \rangle$ has cost of 20, while $\langle (u^\pm, x), (x, v^\pm) \rangle$ for $x \in U$ has cost at least 14. Finally, if $\exists i \in C : u, v \in C_i$, then the path $\langle (u^-, C_i), (C_i, v^-) \rangle$ has cost of at least 9.

- 3) $\forall C_i \in C$, and $\forall u, v \in C_i$ where $u \neq v$, the path $\langle (u^-, C_i), (C_i, v^-) \rangle$ has cost 9 only if either $u \in U_t \wedge u = n_i(v)$ or $v \in U_t \wedge v = n_i(u)$, and 12 otherwise.

Based on these three observations, we will show that all waypoint constraints are satisfied.

- 1) $\forall u \in U : wp(S, u) = (u', u)$. This constraint is satisfied, because $\langle (S, u^\pm), (u^\pm, u'), (u', u) \rangle$ has always cost 15 (using u^+ if $u \in U_t$ and u^- otherwise). Let $v \in U$, where $u \neq v$. Any other path via v^\pm costs at least 17.
- 2) $\forall u \in U : wp(u^\pm, u) = (u^\pm, u')$. We identify three cases:
 - $wp(u^+, u) = (u^+, u')$: The path $\langle (u^+, u'), (u', u) \rangle$ has at most cost 17. Let $v \in U$, where $u \neq v$. Due to Observation 2, any path from u^+ to u that traverses v but not u' will have cost at least $12 + 7 = 19 > 17$.
 - $wp(u^-, u) = (u^-, u')$ and $u \notin U_t$: The path $\langle (u^-, u'), (u', u) \rangle$ has cost 5, which is lower than any other incoming edge of u .
 - $wp(u^-, u) = (u^-, u')$ and $u \in U_t$: The path $\langle (u^-, u'), (u', u) \rangle$ has cost 17. Let $v \in U$, where $u \neq v$. Due to Observation 2, there might exist a path from u^- to u via node v^- with cost $9 + 7 = 16 < 17$. For that, $\exists C_i \in C$ where $u, v \in C_i$. Due to Observation 3, since $u \in U_t$, $n_i(v) = u$. However, rule 10 of Table I assigns cost of 15 to edge (v^-, u) because $u = n_i(v) \implies v \neq n_i(u)$ and because I_{X3SAT} is in canonical form, which means no two variables can be both part of two or more clauses.
- 3) $\forall u, v \in U, u \neq v : wp(u^\pm, v) = (u^\pm, v)$. By Observation 2, The direct path $\langle (u^\pm, v) \rangle$ is the shortest u^\pm - v -path if link (u^\pm, v) has cost 7. However, if there does not exist a $C_i \in C$ where $u, v \in C_i$ and $u = n_i(v)$, then the link (u^-, v) has cost 15. There are many u^- - v -paths, and we argue why each of their cost is larger than 15. In the following, $x \in U \setminus \{u, v\}$, and $C_i \in C$ with $u, v \in C_i$.
 - Any path starting with $\langle (u^-, u'), (u', u^+) \rangle$ already has cost $18 > 15$ and must never be considered.
 - Any path starting with $\langle (u^-, S), (S, x^\pm) \rangle$ already has cost $20 > 15$ and must never be considered.
 - Any path $\langle (u^-, u'), (u', u), (u, x^\pm), (x^\pm, v) \rangle$ has cost at least $3 + 2 + 7 + 7 = 19 > 15$.
 - Any path $\langle (u^-, u'), (u', u), (u, v^\pm), (v^\pm, v'), (v', v) \rangle$ has cost at least $3 + 2 + 7 + 3 + 2 = 17 > 15$.
 - The path $\langle (u^-, C_i), (C_i, v^-), (v^-, v'), (v', v) \rangle$ has cost $3 + 6 + 3 + 2 = 14 < 15$ if and only if $v \notin U_t$ (s.t. (v^-, v') has cost 3), $u \in U_t$ and $u = n_i(v)$ (due to Observation 3). However, by assumption, there cannot exist a clause $C_i \in C$ where $u = n_i(v)$, which is required for link (u^-, v) to have weight 7.
- 4) $\forall C_i \in C, \forall u \in C_i : wp(C_i, u) = (C_i, n_i(u)^-)$. Let $v = n_i(u)$, and let $x = n_i(v)$. We can combine this waypoint with the third constraints, we can see that the only valid path is $p_0 = \langle (C_i^u, v^+), (v^+, u) \rangle$ due to waypoint $wp(v^+, u) = (v^+, u)$. Since C_i has only three outgoing edges towards u^+ , v^+ , and x^+ , for which the waypoint towards u is already proven, we need to show that the path p_0 is smaller than $p_1 = \langle (C_i^u, u^+), (u^+, u'), (u', u) \rangle$. We identify three cases; which of u, v, x is *true*.

- $u \in U_t$: In that case, p_0 has cost $9 + 7 = 16$, because $n_i(n_i(v)) \in U_t$ and $v = n_i(u)$. p_1 has cost $3 + 15 + 2 = 20$, because $u \in U_t$. Similarly, p_2 has cost $6 + 15 = 21$ because $n_i(x) \in U_t$ and $x \neq n_i(u)$.
 - $v \in U_t$: Here, p_0 has cost $3 + 7 = 10$, because $v \in U_t$ and $v = n_i(u)$. p_1 has cost $6 + 3 + 2 = 11$, because $n_i(u) \in U_t$ and $u \notin U_t$. p_2 has cost $9 + 15 = 24$ because $n_i(n_i(x)) \in U_t$ and $x \neq n_i(u)$.
 - $x \in U_t$: Finally, p_0 has cost $6 + 7 = 13$, because $n_i(v) \in U_t$ and $v = n_i(u)$. p_1 has cost $9 + 3 + 2 = 14$, because $n_i(n_i(u)) \in U_t$ and $u \notin U_t$. p_2 has cost $3 + 15 = 18$ because $x \in U_t$ and $x \neq n_i(u)$.
- 5) $\forall C_i \in C, \forall u \in C_i : wp(C_i^u, u) = (C_i^u, n_i(u)^+)$. Let $v = n_i(u)$, and let $x = n_i(v)$. Combining this waypoint with the constraint $wp(v^+, u) = (v^+, u)$, we see that the only path satisfying the requirements is $p_0 = \langle (C_i^u, v^+), (v^+, u) \rangle$. Since C_i^u has only two outgoing edges towards u^+ and v^+ for which we have already shown the waypoint towards u is satisfied, we need to show that the path p_0 is smaller than $p_1 = \langle (C_i^u, u^+), (u^+, u'), (u', u) \rangle$. We distinguish between the three cases, depending on which variable u, v, x is *true*.
 - $u \in U_t$: In that case, p_0 has cost $3 + 7 = 10$, because $u \in U_t$. p_1 has cost $9 + 3 + 2 = 14$, because $n_i(u) \notin U_t$ and $u \in U_t$.
 - $v \in U_t$: Here, p_0 has cost $9 + 7 = 16$, because $u \notin U_t$. p_1 has cost $3 + 15 + 2 = 20$, because $n_i(u) \in U_t$ and $u \notin U_t$.
 - $x \in U_t$: Finally, p_0 has cost $9 + 7 = 16$, because $u \notin U_t$. p_1 has cost $9 + 15 + 2 = 26$, because $n_i(u) \notin U_t$ and $u \notin U_t$.
 - 6) $\forall C_i \in C, \forall u \in C_i : wp(C_i^u, n_i(u)) = (C_i^u, u^+)$. Let $v = n_i(u)$, and let $x = n_i(v)$. The only path satisfying the requirements is $p_0 = \langle (C_i^u, u^+), (u^+, v) \rangle$ because of the waypoint $wp(u^+, v) = (u^+, v)$. Since C_i^u has only two outgoing edges towards u^+ and v^+ for which we have already shown the waypoint towards v is satisfied, we need to show that the path p_0 is smaller than $p_1 = \langle (C_i^u, v^+), (v^+, v'), (v', v) \rangle$. We distinguish between the three cases, depending on which variable u, v, x is *true*.
 - $u \in U_t$: In that case, p_0 has cost $9 + 7 = 16$, because $n_i(u) \notin U_t$. p_1 has cost $3 + 15 + 2 = 20$, because $u \in U_t$ and $v \notin U_t$.
 - $v \in U_t$: Here, p_0 has cost $3 + 7 = 10$, because $n_i(u) \in U_t$. p_1 has cost $9 + 3 + 2 = 14$, because $u \notin U_t$ and $v \in U_t$.
 - $x \in U_t$: Finally, p_0 has cost $9 + 7 = 16$, because $n_i(u) \notin U_t$. p_1 has cost $9 + 15 + 2 = 26$, because $u \notin U_t$ and $v \notin U_t$.

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